

Preliminary Study of the Economic Development Potential of Pageraji Village

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ABSTRACT: This research is a preliminary study using a field study approach. This preliminary study aims to identify natural resources in Pageraji Village that have the potential to be developed to increase the income of the village community. Data collection was conducted by distributing questionnaires and supported by interviews with relevant parties who understand the village's natural conditions. Furthermore, Nvivo software was used to process the interview results regarding the hopes and challenges faced in village development. The results of the study successfully identified that Pageraji Village has natural resources that have the potential to be developed. The presence of coconut trees, land area, and soil and water conditions were identified that could be developed for future agricultural and livestock activities. Based on the coding carried out, it was identified that the natural resources owned by the village are supported by creativity, innovation, community involvement, and government support, providing hope for the development of the village's potential. Furthermore, it was identified that motivation, discipline, conservatism, and the role of institutions are challenges to the development of the village's potential. The results of the study provide insights into the natural resources of Pageraji Village, which in the future can be utilized to develop the village's economic potential. In addition, this research can be continued to deepen other potentials that Pageraji Village has so that later a model can be designed that can be adopted for the development of village potential in general.

KEYWORDS: hopes and challenges, villages, natural resources, village potential development.

1. INTRODUCTION

A village is a legal community unit whose household administration is based on ancestral rights and customs recognized by the central government and located within a regency. Each village should possess potential that can be utilized and developed to improve the welfare of its people. Village potential is all the natural and human resources owned by the village, whether utilized or not (Sukri, 2023).

Pageraji Village, Cilongok, is a village in Banyumas Regency that can be categorized as poor. Pageraji Village's poverty is indicated not only by the condition of its unpaved roads, but also by the fact that most of its residents make their living as laborers and farmers. Furthermore, administrative data is limited in its accessibility, and information about the village is scarce. Therefore, Pageraji Village clearly does not meet the criteria for a developed village, as a developed village is one that has the availability and access to basic services, social activities, economic activities, the environment, accessibility, and good government administration (paralegal.id).

A preliminary survey conducted by researchers on the natural environment of Pageraji village, based on its location, geography, and demographics, indicates that Pageraji village has potential for economic development. However, further study is needed regarding the village's potential. This research focused on natural resource potential. It is well known that appropriate natural resource development will bring greater benefits to the community, for example, by developing it into a tourist village (Sekarsari, 2020), or even into an independent and developed village (Gultom, 2020).

The village's potential can be utilized for regional evaluation and analysis related to economic, social, and infrastructure potential. It can also be used to evaluate implemented programs and serve as a basis for formulating various strategic regional-based policies (Central Statistics Agency, 2018). In general, developing village potential aims to encourage community independence by utilizing the potential of superior natural resources for development (Soleh, 2017).

This research was conducted to identify natural resources in Pageraji Village that have potential for development and how to manage them. The natural resource identification included flora, fauna, soil conditions, and land area. Based on the data obtained, it can then serve as a basis for developing plans for the future development of Pageraji Village's natural resource potential. Therefore, the results of this research will not only benefit Pageraji Village but also be applicable to areas with similar conditions and situations.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

This research uses a mixed methods approach. The data required for this study consist of primary and secondary data. Primary data are direct sources that provide data for researchers, such as interviews and questionnaires. Secondary data are indirect sources that provide data for researchers. These data are obtained from sources that can support the research, such as literature and documentation (Sugiyono, 2022).

Data collection was conducted through field studies, questionnaire distribution, and interviews. The field study was conducted to determine the actual physical condition of Pageraji Village. The questionnaire distribution was conducted to obtain data related to the respondents' identities, as well as answers regarding the village's natural resource potential, their hopes for future village development, and challenges facing village development implementation. Interviews were conducted to reconfirm the answers written by respondents on the questionnaire.

Respondents were selected using a purposive method, where the sample population used for the study was deliberately selected to reflect certain characteristics such as age, location, or even species (Patton, 2014). Respondents in this study were those who met the following criteria:

1. Adult age
2. Have received an education (can read and write)
3. Are representatives of parties who understand village conditions.

Data obtained from the questionnaires and interviews were then processed using NVivo software. Nvivo software was chosen because it is suitable for qualitative and mixed methods research, specifically for analyzing unstructured text, audio, video, and image data, including interviews, focus groups, surveys, social media, and journal articles (libguides.library.kent.edu).

3. RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

1. Respondent Description

The questionnaires were completed by community organizations, community leaders, non-partisan community organizations (Karang Taruna), entrepreneurs, artists, livestock breeders, and even housewives. Twenty questionnaires were collected and used for further analysis. Interviews were also conducted to confirm the answers provided. Table 1 presents a description of the study respondents:

Table 1. Respondent Description

Description	Sum	Proportion
Gender:		
Male	19	95%
Female	1	5%
Total	20	100%
Education background:		
Elementary School	3	15%
Junior High School	8	40%
Senior High School	8	40%
Bachelor	1	5%
Total	20	100%

2. Results of Natural Resource Potential Analysis

The data analysis shows that Pageraji Village has potential natural resources that can be developed. The following are key points from the research findings:

1. The vegetation in the village is dominated by coconut trees.
2. The most popular livestock among residents are goats.

- 3. The natural conditions are quite fertile due to favorable weather and the availability of a steady river water supply.
- 4. There is 10 hectares of land that has not been optimally utilized.

3. Results of the Analysis of Hopes and Challenges for Village Potential Development

The results of the analysis using the NVivo tool with a coding approach to informants' answers regarding expectations regarding the development of village potential are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. NVivo output based on coding expectations regarding village potential development

The results of the analysis using the NVivo tool with a coding approach to informants' answers regarding expectations regarding the development of village potential are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. NVivo output based on coding challenges to village potential development

D. Discussions

Research indicates that Pageraji Village has natural resources with potential for development. The presence of coconut trees, goats, natural conditions, and land area are important factors.

1. Coconut trees offer numerous economic benefits, both from their fruit and their sap (Salsabila et al., 2025).
2. Goats are low-maintenance, have a relatively high market value, and can be optimized to reduce plant waste and provide food, and their manure can be used as fertilizer (digitani.ipb.ac.id).
3. The relatively fertile natural conditions, along with the presence of a flowing river, offer potential for both agriculture and fisheries (pe.feb.unesa.ac.id).
4. Underutilized land has the potential to be optimized for both farming and livestock farming (www.papayan.desa.id).

Furthermore, regarding expectations for village development potential, it is known that the village's natural resources, supported by creativity, innovation, community involvement, and government support, are factors that contribute to optimism for successful village development. Meanwhile, regarding challenges to village potential, it is known that motivation, discipline, conservatism, and the role of institutions are factors that contribute to pessimism regarding the success of village development.

4. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE RESEARCH AGENDA

A. Conclusions

Pageraji Village has natural resource potential that can be developed in the future. The presence of coconut trees, goats, relatively fertile natural conditions, and vacant land provide natural resources with the potential for further development. Development of Pageraji Village's natural resource potential can be achieved by optimizing land for agriculture, livestock, and fisheries.

Hopes and challenges are two aspects that must be considered for the successful development of the village's potential. Hope arises from the community's understanding of the village's potential, but behind this lies the challenge that must be overcome to successfully develop its natural resource potential. Therefore, among the many factors identified, collaboration between the community and the government is the most important consideration.

B. Limitations and Future Research Agendas

This research is a preliminary study that only identifies natural resource potential; therefore, further research identifying human resource potential can be conducted. Without discrediting the educational background of the respondents, this study is limited in exploring the research findings, so it appears that many factors emerged from the coding results. The researcher simplified the research results with the aim of making it easier for readers to understand the research results, not to eliminate or ignore the answers given by respondents. Future research would be better if it could extend the interview period and include personnel capable of acting as communication mediators between researchers and respondents.

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